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WORK-LIFE BALANCE
IN GREEK WOMEN
EMPLOYEES
EOX GRO7/3672

Με τη συγχρηματοδότηση της Ελλάδας και του Χρηματοδοτικού Μηχανισμού ΕΟΧ 2009-2014

INTRODUCTION

“Work-Life Balance in Greek Women Employees” is a project which aims to examine various factors related to work-life balance in women employees and suggest a model that could explain work-life balance phenomenon in Greek reality and suggesting a number of potential risk and protective factors.

Objectives:

- To offer an in-depth description of the situation as regards work-life phenomenon in female population in Greece, especially under the pressure of the financial crisis.
- To examine and suggest the main risk factors for the lack of work-life balance in Greek women, as well as potential protective factors.
- To examine and describe potential negative consequences of work-life conflict in occupational and personal life.
- To suggest and test a methodology which can be followed in future studies.
- To test a training curriculum and how effective could be to improve work-life balance among women employees.
- To provide stakeholders with some recommendations for policy reform and plans.
- To increase job satisfaction, quality of life and the balance between work and life.

Project's Impact:

Knowledge on the topic of Women's Work-Life Balance (and various aspects) in Greek reality will be increased.

Partners will develop and test a research design and tools which will be in the disposal of researchers for further research of the topic.

Educational material/an intervention program for increasing work-life balance will be suggested, and organizations/companies could use it in order to facilitate women employees to achieve work-life balance.

Greek women employees who will participate in the project will increase their knowledge about potential risk factors for work-life conflict and potential protective variables that they could focus on.

Women employees are going to improve their productivity and the quality of the working outputs, decrease conflicts in work, as well as decrease job absence and leavings

Finally, we expect that our research results will support policy reforms regarding employment issues for Greek women at workplace.

According to OECD findings (<http://www.oecdbetterlifeindex.org/responses/#GRC>), Greek people have reported higher work rates, 2,109 hours a year, in comparison with the average of 1,749 hours in European countries. The Regus Survey (2010-2012) (<http://www.slideshare.net/REGUSmedia/regus-worklife-balance-white-paper>) on Work-Life Balance indicated that there is deterioration Greek worker life (in comparison with 2010). 74% of the employees report that work more hours than in 2010, due to the financial crisis. The increase in unemployment rates and the economic instability of the country seem to have affected negatively the quality of life of Greek people, and have increased the levels of stress and depressive symptoms. The situation above has appeared to force Greek people to make a harder effort to find a harmonious balance between work and personal life. Moreover, data from the European Working Conditions Observatory (EWCO) indicate that some countries, such as Greece, Portugal, Spain and Ireland do not have flexible working hours for parents who work in a full time job. More specifically in Greece, women who work in full time paid jobs, are the main responsible people to take care of their family and at the same time to deal with the increased work responsibilities. As a result Greek women employees report that they do not have enough recreational time and feel overwhelmed because of their heavy program (<http://businessculture.org/southern-europe/business-culture-in-greece/work-life-balance-in-greece/>).

Although, according to OECD findings Greece ranks above the average in some dimensions such as health status, work-life balance and personal security, they report lower levels in dimensions such as education and skills, income and wealth, civic engagement, jobs and earnings, social connections, housing, subjective well-being and environmental quality. Because of the changes in the occupational area and employment situation (due to financial crisis) people report lower levels of life satisfaction (from 59% to 34% people who feel satisfaction from their life in general). Additionally, according to the Eurobarometer survey, Greek people are the most dissatisfied ones in Europe as regards the work-life balance. Based on the data above the consortium of "Work-life Balance in Greek Women Employees" decided to conduct a research program focusing on women employees in Greece examining various factors related to work life balance, suggesting and confirming a model that could explain work-life balance phenomenon in Greek reality and suggesting a number of potential risk and protective factors.

The following Training Material is the content of the Research Intervention which has been conducted in order to examine the role of specific soft skills development, based on a previous piloting European Program, on the work-life balance achievement. The Training Curriculum is based on the Handbook of the "Balance" project and specific modules have been used to create the training program and material. The training curriculum includes some theoretical presentations and experiential activities (based on non-formal education) aiming at the development of soft skills which seem to relate to work-life balance. Ten women participated in this intervention program and completed two scales about soft skills level and work life balance (baseline measurement). Then they attained the training course/intervention aiming at the soft skills development and one month after the completion of the intervention program, the participants will complete the same scales in order to examine any changes in the soft skills level and its association with improved work-life balance reports. The main aim, is to examine the role of specific soft skills such as self-awareness, time management, creativity, planning and networking on the work-life achievement. This training program is based on the salutogenic model, which focuses on the development of the healthy aspects of individuals.

MODULE 1: MYSELF/SELF-AWARENESS (Duration 3hours)

DESCRIPTION OF MODULE:

Self-knowledge and self-assessment can be considered as crucial individual resources in order to ensure a balanced attitude toward work related stress and personal life satisfaction.

The self/self-awareness module having included concepts such as self-perception, values, emotional competences and motivation covers a significant area of Emotional Intelligence idea, which play an important role to work-life balance and quality of life. Emotional intelligence has been associated with sense of coherence (SOC) concept of salutogenesis and both of them with health behaviors and health indicators.

The self-perception topic and the related exercises aim at making participants aware of different but complementary parts of themselves. It helps them to accept the ambiguity of their human nature and be more prepared to use the available (internal and external) resources. This is relevant to the two core concepts of salutogenic theory: the sense of coherence and the generalized resistance resources.

This module also focuses on the positive/healthy aspects of a personality and do not stress on deficit-oriented approaches (fundamental principle of salutogenic model). Women may face stressful situations that challenge their personal resources and they "learn" to shed light on the negative aspects. Adapting a positive attitude toward oneself and others may facilitate a person to engage in a more functional cognitive processing (focusing on abilities and strong points) and use active/problem solving coping mechanisms. Namely she is able to identify, use and re-use the appropriate resources in order to manage work-life balance.

Moreover, women need to unearth hidden emotions to support work-life balance. According to salutogenic model and more specifically the Comprehensibility/ cognitive element of Sense of Coherence concept, hidden emotions may prevent someone to perceive those stimuli (internal or external) that confront her. People can perceive those stimuli as information that is well-ordered, consistent, structured, and clear and as making cognitive sense.

Main idea for this module is to give to participants an opportunity to understand their selves, their values, their inner potential, and at the end, to realize the importance of this capacity in their everyday balance. By this mean, this module aims to rise up participants' Self - Awareness. Self-awareness basically describes a situation where the light of awareness is turned onto ourselves. While awareness is our ability to take note; self-awareness is our ability to take note of ourselves.

The world of the self is rich and fascinating and we are privileged to possess the ability to actually enjoy all of this consciously. Our capacity for awareness is what makes this possible.

MODULE TOPICS:

- Self-awareness
- Values

CONTENTS OF TRAINING INTERVENTION

ICEBREAKER AND NAME GAMES

1. CANDIES

Aim:

Candies is a get-to-know-you game which helps people learn new facts about each other in an easy and fun way. Participants select various pieces of candy from a bag, and each candy variety is associated with a fact about themselves which they will introduce to the others.

Setup:

Several variety packs of candy, enough for each person to be able to have at least five pieces. They can be any candy type, but not too many choices (limit it to around five different varieties).

Instructions:

Pass around the candy and tell each participant to choose anywhere from 1 to 5 pieces of anything that they want. Instruct them not to eat it yet, though. After they have chosen their candy, you will tell them what each candy type/color represents.

If there is a whiteboard or chalkboard present, write on the board the following:

- Red - Favorite hobbies
- Green - Favorite place on earth
- Blue - Favorite memory
- Yellow - Dream job
- Orange - Wildcard (tell us anything about yourself)

If you don't have the above colors, change the above to match the candy types that you have.

Each person takes turns introducing himself or herself, beginning with their name and then saying one fact for each candy type that they have.

2. YARN WEB

Aim

To practice participants names and emphasize the dynamic of a group and the importance of commitment in the learning process, which means between more, an active and consistent participation.

Setup

A ball of wool.

Instructions:

The first person of the circle holds the ball of the wool in their hand introduces themselves and then they throw the ball of wool to any other person in the circle, while holding on to the beginning of the ball of wool and saying the name of that person. The second person in turn holds the remaining of the ball of wool throws the ball to another participant while calling his name and while holding on to part of the ball of wool. . A spider web is formed with the wool once every one has introduced themselves. When the web has been formed, the facilitator, explains the importance of the presence of the whole group during the training meetings in order the web to remain tide and complete. Facilitator can also give an example that in case someone leaves the string they are holding then the web ceases to be strong and everything will fall apart. All participants can cut a piece of the wool they are holding and make possibly a reminder-bracelet which will wear during the entire Training Intervention.

3. FEARS AND EXPECTATIONS

Aim

To enable learners to express their hopes, fears & expectations about the training intervention & to acknowledge & affirm peers & tutor as a source of support.

Setup

3 sets different colored 'post it' sticky notes-yellow, orange, green.

Instructions:

Part 1: Distribute 3 post-its to each participant: Instruct participants to identify key hopes on 1 st (yellow), key fears on 2nd (orange), and key expectations on 3 rd (Green). No names attached.

Part 2: Viewing 3 boards or flipchart sheet placed around room - each participant places post-it in appropriate place. Participants circulate around room to view others' postings.

Part 3: Ask whole group what they consider the main (1) hope (2) fear (3) expectation Facilitator to discuss Training Meetings' expectations with regard to previous input on structure & content of course. Facilitator to point out that most fears/concerns/anxieties are shared & that group can be a source of support.

4. SETTING RULES OF TRAINING

All participants are discussing the "rules" they want to establish in order the training process to be effective. The rules are written on the blackboard in order to be visible by everyone through the whole Training Intervention's duration.

SELF-AWARENESS

Aim and objectives:

Participants will acquire a better perception regarding their personal needs. They will focus on their inner self. They will enhance their self-awareness and will set goals towards an increased level of life satisfaction. Participants will set personal priorities and they will be able to evaluate their needs in order to succeed inner peace and life satisfaction.

Presentation of Training Module aim and objectives/PowerPoint attached (annex 1).

- To understand my strengths.
- To discover my core life values.
- To understand my reactions and behaviors in relation to my values.
- To understand what motivates me.
- To get a better understanding of my priorities and enhance my self-awareness in order to succeed work-life balance.

WHEEL OF LIFE (annex 2)

This wheel contains eight sections that, together, represent one way of describing a whole life. Taking the center of the wheel as O and the outer edge as an ideal IO , the participants first rate the above mentioned areas regarding the importance those areas have for them. (i.e. How important is money for you?).

After that, participants complete the wheel once more but this time they rate their level of satisfaction with each life area by drawing a straight or curved line to create a new outer edge. This exercise measures the level of satisfaction in these areas on the day they work through this exercise. The new perimeter represents their Wheel of Life.

How bumpy would the ride be if this were a real wheel? Comparing the two wheels what information participants get? Let's start to look at areas where they want to improve their level of satisfaction and think about what they might do to accomplish that.

MIND YOUR CHOCOLATE

Part 1: Have everybody sit comfortably and show them a large bar of chocolate. Ask the group if they know where chocolate comes from? Do they know the ingredients in it? Do they know how many people were involved in the process to bring it here?

• Read out the 'Did You Know?':

DID YOU KNOW? The tasty secret of the cacao tree was discovered 2,000 years ago in the tropical rainforests of Mexico and Central America. Ancient people mixed ground cacao seeds with chilli peppers and cornmeal to make a spicy, frothy drink. It wasn't until the 1500s that Europeans tasted chocolate brought back to Spain from the Americas. A cacao pod contains about 30-50 almond-sized seeds - enough to make about seven milk chocolate bars!

Part 2: Ensure that everyone is comfortable, and distribute squares of chocolate. The group should hold the square in their hand, then close their eyes and listen. Read out the following to the group: "Feel the weight and shape of your chocolate. Bring it to your nose. Smell the chocolate. How does it smell? How does your body respond to the smell? Is your mouth watering? Now, with your eyes still closed, place the chocolate in your mouth and let it rest on your tongue. Can you taste the chocolate? If so, where can you taste it - tongue, cheeks, palate, throat? As the chocolate rests in your mouth, think of the cocoa bean it was. Can you imagine what the bean looks like? What it feels like? Again notice your chocolate. Is it still on your tongue? Can you still taste it? And smell it? With your eyes closed, swallow it. Can you follow the chocolate as it travels down your throat and into your stomach? When you're ready, open your eyes."

Discussion:

Was this different to how you normally eat chocolate? How?

When you taste food, do you taste all parts of it?

What did you learn from eating the chocolate 'mindfully'?

What other things can we do mindfully?

What difference would it make to life if we all did things mindfully?

The Should Exercise

Background:

We all have internalized rules and messages that we carry around inside us. In Gestalt, these messages are known as introjections – something we swallowed whole and haven't "chewed on" enough to see if it's truly our own desire/rule, or if we've just absorbed it from the outside world. Every time you hear "I should" in your head/voice, it's a sign that you might be dealing with an introjection – and thus it's an invitation for you to take a closer look.

Step one: "I should" as a woman.

Spend ten minutes or so writing down all the "I should"s or "I shouldn't"s that regularly come into your mind.

Examples:

I should take care of my household

I should take care about my husband

I should communicate often with my parents in law.

Step two: "You should"

One statement at a time, ask someone you trust to read your list back to you, reading it as "You should...".

So, my partner would say, "You should pay off debt."

After each statement my partner reads to me, I take a moment to:

notice any internal feelings or emotions that come up in me as I hear the statement.

notice whether it feels like my own voice, something I truly want to do, or whether it's someone else's voice (e.g. often someone has a "should" statement that really belongs to a parent, and as soon as they hear someone else say "You should..." they recognize that this statement is their parent's voice, not their own inner guide).

Step three: Decide and Take Ownership

After each statement my partner reads to me, I decide if “I will” or “I won’t”, and then I report the new statement back to them.

Example:

My partner: “You should pay off debt.”

Me: “I will pay off debt.”

(Or, “I won’t pay off debt.”)

(Or, “I will pay off debt within five years.”)

(Or, “I will not focus on paying off debt until I finish school.”)

Whatever you choose – whether you will, or won’t, or under which conditions – is fine. The key part is that instead of carrying around an unexamined “I should”, a statement weighing you down with judgment, you are now carrying around a decision that you have made and owned yourself.

It can be incredibly liberating to move from, “I should practice the piano more,” to “You know what? I don’t want to. I won’t.”

It can be empowering to move from, “I should organize my time better,” to “I will be highly organized from 8am-12pm every day, and after that will work in an unstructured way.”

Whether you’re already smitten with this exercise or not, I invite you to give it a try and see what you discover.

POWEPPOINT PRESENTATION OF VALUES THEORY (annex 1)

During the training intervention the below mentioned exercises and tools coming from coaching approach were used by adjusting them for being suitable to a group of people. Through questions and scenarios, participants can get the assistance in order to detect their core values. Trainer is always available to answer questions and assist. The below mentioned exercises are individual exercises. The importance of confidentiality was one more time pointed out.

VALUES

Aim and objectives:

Participants will discover and prioritize their values of life. Participants will self evaluate their level of satisfaction and will possibly discover suppression of their basic values which usually lead to negative feelings and behaviors.

VALUES (annex 3) WORKSHEETS

A. Values Clarification Exercise:

The first tip is to use a pencil with an eraser. Participants often experience a sense of reluctance when values have to be written in ink. The trainer can emphasize the advantages of using a pencil so the participants realize that it is not important to get it right the first time. The second tip when doing values clarification is to use several words together to form a string describing the value. Separating the words with slash marks makes the string easier to read. For example:

Integrity/Honesty/Walk-the-talk
Integrity/Whole/Congruent
Leadership/Empower/Collaborative
Leadership/Decisive/Powerful

When creating the values string, ask the participants to place the most significant term at the beginning, such as “Integrity” and “Leadership” in the examples above.

Point out that it may take several months to come up with a fairly complete list of values. Since values show up over time in our lives, it is unlikely that we will be able to capture them accurately and completely in one sitting. Values that are fully defined and elaborated on become a powerful tool in pointing participants toward fulfilling choices as they approach a major crossroads or get off track. The trainer facilitates the process of identifying values by proposing various scenarios to the participants. The following scenarios will give you a place to start. Experiment with these and continue to explore other methods for allowing clients to see their values.

Trainer can help participants to identify their values by probing the following questions:

A Peak Moment in Time

Ask participants to identify special, peak moments when life was especially rewarding or poignant. It’s important that the time frame be quite limited—a “moment”—or there will be too much in the experience to allow the participants to pinpoint specific values.

Set questions like: “What was happening?” “Who was present and what was going on?” “What were the values that were being honored in that moment?” “Is there a value of accomplishment or achievement in that experience?” Keep looking at peak moments, seeking experiences participants found particularly rich and fulfilling.

Suppressed Values

Another way to isolate values is to go to the opposite extreme, looking at times when you were angry, frustrated, or upset. This will often lead to identification of a value that was being suppressed.

For example, one might say, “I felt trapped, backed into a corner. I had no choices.” The trainer might then say, “Trapped, cornered, without choice. If we flip that over, it sounds like there might be a value around freedom or options or choice. For the trainer, it’s not so important that the vocabulary be right—it’s important that the words feel right to the participants.

Many of us have created our lives in such a way that we automatically and easily honor many of our values without even being aware that we are doing so. Therefore we may not recognize them as values until something gets in the way. The key here is to point out to the client that every upset or moment of distress is likely to signal that a value is being suppressed.

Must-Haves

Another way for participants to identify their values is to look at what they must have in their lives. Try it yourself. Beyond the physical requirements of food, shelter, and community, what must you have in your life in order to be fulfilled?

Must you have a form of creative self-expression? Must you have adventure and excitement in your life? Must you have partnership and collaboration? Must you be moving toward a sense of accomplishment or success or be surrounded with natural beauty? An underlying question for the process is: What are the values you absolutely must honor—or part of you dies?

Obsessive Expression

We are all capable of obsessive behavior—insisting on honoring a value, inflating it into a demand rather than a form of self-expression. You've probably had an experience like this in your own life, such as when your roommate's value of orderliness became an obsessive demand for perfection. Our friends and families often do us a service by pointing out the obsessive expression of our values: "You are so controlling!" "All you think about is your students." "You want all the attention." These statements might point toward a value of personal power/leadership, of learning/growth, and of recognition/acknowledgment. Have your participants examine those times when they take certain values to the extreme. "What is it that people say about you? What do you say about yourself?" "What is it that people tease you about or that drives them crazy?" There are important values here that have mutated for some reason. Look for the value, and don't focus on the mutation.

Hand them the worksheet "Values Clarification Exercise"

B. Values-based Decision Matrix

One of the most potent tools for making fulfilling life choices is the Values-Based Decision Matrix. This matrix is launched during the initial values clarification process. After participants have brainstormed and written down a list of values, ask them to rank the top 5 values in priority order. Then ask participants to score their sense of satisfaction—the degree to which they are honoring each value—using a scale of 0 to 10. Most participants find this exercise very revealing, and they are often shocked at what they learn about themselves. It has been noted that when things are going particularly well in someone's life, the scores typically are high. When someone is struggling or is at a low point, the values matrix can help determine where corrective action is needed. When a person is facing a major decision, such as whether to make a job change or start a new business, or even to have a child, the Values-Based Decision Matrix can be particularly revealing.

–Ask participants to score their values today. Next, ask them to project out two months, a year, or sometime in the future: "Imagine that you did make the change. Anticipate and write down what your scores would be if you did. Next, imagine that you did not make the change and record those scores." This exercise will provide participants with useful insight about making a fulfilling choice. Note how provocative and revealing such an examination can be. What are not on such list of values are tangible measures, such as money and status—factors that are usually the basis for decision making yet rarely lead to fulfilling choices.

VISUALIZATION-Future Self Exercise

Have participants get comfortable, perhaps lower the light level, make sure there will be no distractions, and play quiet, meditative music. When participants are grounded and ready, begin the visualization. Pause at appropriate times throughout the visualization to give the participants sufficient time to be with the location or answer the questions. Allow a little time at the end for debriefing, respecting the will of participants to not wanting to share personal information. Focus more on the experience of doing the exercise and not on the content.

INSTRUCTIONS:

Get into a comfortable position. Now allow your eyes to close and begin by focusing your awareness on your breath. Breathing in and breathing out. Breathing in easily and effortlessly. Then breathing out. Each breath allows you to become more relaxed and comfortable. Outside sounds only allow you to go deeper inside: a reminder of how good it is to leave the noise and stress of the outside world and journey into the quiet and peace of your inner world. (Include the next paragraph only when you want the client to go to an even deeper meditative space.) As you allow yourself to go deeper into a state of relaxation, perhaps you can remember a time when you stood before a pond or a lake and it was quiet and peaceful. You may have tossed a pebble into the center and noticed the ripples spreading out. One ripple after another, flowing outward, farther and farther. The ripples slowing down, becoming farther apart, until the water was once again calm and peaceful. I'm going to invite you now to imagine that your body is like that body of water. And as you drop a pebble into the center of your body, you can feel ripples of relaxation rippling out. Waves of relaxation flowing through your body. Up through your torso into your chest and your back. Up through the vertebrae and spreading out into each and every muscle of your back. Through your shoulders and arms, up through your neck, your jaw, face, scalp. Feeling those ripples relax you as your muscles let go and become soft and loose. Feeling the ripples of relaxation flowing down through the bottom of your torso. Flowing through your abdomen and your pelvis. Down through your thighs, calves, ankles, and toes. Know that each time you drop a pebble into the center of your body you can become more relaxed.

As you become more relaxed, you find yourself becoming more quiet and peaceful. Now bring your attention to the spot between your eyes: the third eye. Imagine a light there. What color is the light between your eyes? Now imagine that light becoming a beam that extends out into space. Follow that beam as it leaves this building, as it travels above the city, as it continues out, so that you can view the entire area. Keep going farther and farther into outer space and notice the curvature of the earth. As you keep going farther and farther out, you find yourself enveloped by the softness and quiet of space. Notice the big blue-green ball below you with the white clouds wisping around it. Allow yourself to enjoy this perspective for a moment. Now notice another beam of light very near to you, a different color from the one you followed into outer space. Begin to follow that beam back down to earth. The beam is taking you back to earth twenty years from now, twenty years into the future. Keep following this beam down, noticing the curvature of the earth and the geography stretched out below you. As you come closer to the end of the beam, keep

noticing where you are. This is where your future self lives—you, twenty years from now. Come into contact with earth and notice where you are. Notice what dwelling or nature surrounds you. Now move to the dwelling of your future self.

What does it look like? What kind of landscape does it have? Are there trees? Flowers? What kind? Get a sense of this place. Now have someone come to the door. On the other side of the door is your future self, waiting to greet you—yourself, twenty years from now. As the door opens, what do you notice? Greet your future self and notice the way your future self returns your greeting, welcoming you into this time and place twenty years in the future. Take in this person, your future self. What does this person look like? Notice how this person stands, what this person is wearing. Get a sense of this person's essence. Notice the inside of this dwelling. What kind of person lives here? What are the colors of this place? Now move with your future self to a comfortable place for a conversation. Perhaps your future self offers you something to drink. Settle in and make yourself comfortable for a talk with your future self. There are questions that you might want to ask your future self. Begin by asking: "What is it that you most remember about the past twenty years?" Take a moment now to hear the answer. (Pause) Now ask your future self the following question: "What do I need to know to get me from where I am now to where you are? What would be most helpful?" Listen to what your future self has to tell you. (Pause) Good. Now take a moment and ask your future self your own questions. What other questions would you like to ask your future self? (Pause) And now ask your future self one final question before you go: "What name, other than your first name, are you called by? A special name. It could be a metaphor or a symbol of your essence.

What is this name?" (Pause) Good. Bringing this visit to a close, thank your future self for being here with you today and sharing so much wisdom. Now find your way back to the beam of light and journey back up the beam, watching this world of twenty years in the future grow ever smaller as you move out into space. Again, you see the ball of blue and green below you, clouds swirling around it. Notice that your beam of light has intersected with a different beam of light that will bring you back to this year and this location. Follow this beam of light back to the present time on earth. As you travel down this beam, notice the earth growing bigger and bigger. Moving farther down the beam, notice the geography of the area, the skyline and landscape of the area, and, finally, come back into the room here. Good. In a few moments, I'm going to count from three to one. At the count of one, you will be refreshed and alert, as if you've had the perfect amount of rest, knowing you can remember everything you wish of this inner journey. When you open your eyes, please remain silent and jot down things you want to remember about your journey. Three. Coming back to present time, becoming more alert and refreshed. Two. Stretching your body, feeling the ground beneath you. And one. Eyes open, refreshed and alert.

LETTER TO SELF

Aim

Increase self-reflection and awareness. Setting future goals.

Setup

A4, Pen and Envelopes

Instructions

Give each 1) paper or postcard and 2) envelope.

Ask each person to write a note to themselves-including today's date-highlighting key points they have learned from the workshop or things they would like to bring more of into their life or perhaps an inspiring or thoughtful message for themselves. You can ask participants to put anything they want on there. It could be goals, learnings, dreams, questions, reminders.

Next ask each person to fill out their addresses on the envelope, put in their "Note to Self" and seal the envelope.

3/6/12 months later, you post the "Note to Self" to your workshop attendees.

WRAP UP/EVALUATION

Ask from participants to sit again in circle. Ask them to share one word they want, describing their experience from today's workshop. That one word can be a thought, a feelings etc.

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ANNEXES

ANNEX 1

MYSELF

- SELF AWARENESS
 - VALUES

OBJECTIVES

- To understand my strengths.
- To discover my core life values.
- To understand my reactions and behaviors in relation to my values.
- To understand what motivates me.
- To get a better understanding of my priorities and enhance my self-awareness in order to succeed work-life balance.

VALUES

Values are who we are. Not who we would like to be, not who we think we should be, but who we are in our lives, right now. Another way to put it is that values represent our unique and individual essence, our ultimate and most fulfilling form of expressing and relating. Our values serve as a compass pointing out what it means to be true to oneself. When we honor our values on a regular and consistent basis, life is good and fulfilling. Important life decisions are easier to make and outcomes are more fulfilling when the decisions are viewed through a matrix of well-understood personal values. However, the process of clarifying values is often difficult for clients.

It frequently makes people intellectualize and fantasize, whereas you want them to look into their lives and uncover the values that are already there, in their day-to-day actions and interactions. That's one of the reasons selecting values from a list seldom works: the list becomes an opportunity to vote on the most desirable or socially acceptable values, rather than serving as a mechanism to identify who we are. Selecting values from a list reinforces the intellectual urge to figure it out and get the words right. People's values are observable; they live in the world. Thus, they won't benefit from picking their values from a list.

Values clarification exercises allows clients to examine and articulate their values in a safe yet courageous environment. The exact wording will matter to the client in the long run, but what is most important in the short run is that the approximate label for the value resonate with the participant.

ANNEX 2

MODULE 2: MY NETWORK (Duration 3hours)

“My Network” module emphasizes on relationship dynamics and successful communication. The module focuses on basic skills of assertiveness and negotiation which result to effective communication style and balanced relationships. Groups dynamics as well as the roles each individual choose or/and is called to take, influence how those people perceive their everyday problems and how they act to deal with them. The concept “self-actualization”, as well as its importance for personal health, has been used in this framework. It would be useful to mention some characteristics (e.g acceptance, realism, autonomy and solitude) of self-actualized people and how those factors are related to work-life balance and health promotion. Maslow’ self- actualization concept focuses on human potentiality, and how we fulfill that potentiality, instead of focusing on what goes wrong with people. This concept is a related to salutogenesis concept.

Negotiation has effectively been chosen to describe how the work-family balance can be succeeded. The work/family border theory (Clark, 2000) explains how individuals manage and negotiate the work and family spheres and the borders between them in order to attain balance and avoid conflicts. Negotiation, also, facilitates someone to keep relationships and therefore to save important resources (material and non-material) to use them and re-use them when he/she is in need. The two above comments are associated with salutogenesis model, which focuses on the relationship between resources and health endorsement.

Network may have a profound influence on one another’s health and happiness. (Christakis, 2000). People who develop clear and supportive networks are able to identify external resources, use them and reuse them, satisfy needs and cope with different problems (Eriksson and Lindström, 2007). The above can be a health improvement process according the salutogenic model.

MODULE TOPICS:

- Conflict resolution
- Styles of Communication: Assertiveness
- Negotiation

CONTENTS OF TRAINING INTERVENTION

NAME GAME/ENERGIZER

Aim:

Remembering names of the groups. Energize the group. Ice-breaker activity.

Setup:

3 small balls

Instructions

All participants stand in a circle and by throwing to another person a small ball and saying the name of that person, they practice the names of the group. After a while, facilitator enters a new ball in the circle which also is being circulated and participants are calling each other names. You can also add one more ball for energizing the group more.

CONFLICT RESOLUTION

Handling aggression

Aim:

To introduce the topic of conflict resolution to the group.

Setup:

A person unknown to the group

Instructions:

Unbeknownst to the participants, have someone primed to burst into the room claiming angrily that they have booked this meeting room and can the group please leave so they can set up. Then trainer will 'freeze' the 'intruder' and discuss different options for responding to this aggressive outburst, before trying each one out to see what effect it has.

Conflict close up

Aim:

To understand our initial reactions to conflict

To consider how our reactions may influence the outcome of the conflict

Setup:

None

Instructions:

Stand in the center of the room and announce the following to the group: I am conflict. Consider how you typically react when you experience a personal conflict. Position yourself, in relation to me, somewhere in the room in a way that conveys your initial response to a conflict. Pay attention to your body language as well as your distance from the conflict.

Tips Use this activity twice—once near the beginning of the program and then again at the end—to get a visual picture regarding changes in positions as a result of considering conflict differently.

Discussion Questions

1. What are some reasons you are standing where you are?
2. If where you are standing signifies your initial reaction, where might you stand after taking some time to think about the conflict?
3. What are some things that would cause you to move?
4. How might our reactions influence the course of the conflict?

How do you see it?

Aim:

- To understand our perception of conflict
- To consider a different perspective on conflict
- To learn techniques to better handle conflict
- To build trust

Setup:

- One copy of the Conflict-How Do You See It? handout (Annex 1) for each participant,
- Pens

Instructions:

Conflict can provide the spark that often leads to better solutions, creativity, and collaboration. This activity helps team members to: (1) become more comfortable with conflict, (2) consider the positive aspects of conflict, and (3) understand the possible benefits to themselves and the team. Have participants pair up. Provide each person with a copy of the handout. Allow 10 to 15 minutes for partners to interview each other. Follow with a group discussion of the interviews and then go over the discussion questions. Have team members switch partners every three questions to increase the level of trust within the team.

Discussion Questions

1. Were your partner's perspectives different from your perspective?
2. What were some things you learned by considering another's perspective?
3. Does discussing conflict like this make it "less scary"? In what ways?
4. Is conflict good or bad?
5. What are some ways in which conflict is detrimental to the team?
6. What are some ways in which conflict enriches the team?

Bull's Eye

Aim:

- To understand that how we deal with conflict impacts ourselves, our team, and the organization
- To look at the big-picture benefits of effective conflict resolution

Setup:

- Flip-chart paper, markers, paper, pens

Instructions:

Draw a large target (consisting of three circles, one inside the other) on the flip-chart paper. · The innermost circle represents the team members themselves.

· The middle circle represents the team.

· The outer circle represents the company.

Ask, "How does effectively resolving conflicts affect you, your team, and your organization/company?" As team members shout out various ideas, record them in the appropriate place on the target.

You can create two targets: one for the benefits of effective conflict resolution and one for ineffective conflict management skills, and how each impacts the individual, the team, and the organization/company.

Discussion Questions

1. How does your ability to resolve conflicts affect you in your job?

2. How does a team member's ability to resolve conflicts impact the team/colleagues?

3. How does a team's ability to resolve conflicts impact the organization/company etc?

Step by step

Aim:

To discover the steps to effective conflict resolution

To create a conflict-resolution process that can be used in any conflict

To create buy-in to the conflict-resolution process

Setup:

Copy paper, markers, painter's tape

Instructions:

Split your group into smaller teams of four to seven participants. Station the teams in different areas throughout the room. Ask each team to write the word Conflict on one sheet of paper and the word Resolution on another. Instruct them to tape the sheets of paper about six feet apart on a nearby wall. Invite the teams to brainstorm the specific steps necessary to get from "Conflict" to "Resolution." As the steps are agreed upon, have team members write them on sheets of paper and place them on the wall between the "Conflict" and "Resolution" sheets.

Discussion Questions

1. What has to happen right before "Resolution"?

2. Is there an additional step after "Resolution"? What could be added?

3. How does it benefit us to have a step-by-step approach to conflict?

4. How can we remember these steps in conflict situations?

Styles of communication: Assertiveness (Annex 2)

Presenting and discussing the theory of different styles of communication: Passive, Assertive and Aggressive, as well as techniques for an effective assertive communication.

Participants first receive a form of self-evaluation regarding assertiveness skills and then the group discuss on the notes given.

*Handouts to participants

Negotiation

Arm wrestle

Aim:

Practice Negotiation skills/ understand the importance of dismantling assumptions and developing a collaborative approach when people assume that more for one person means less for the other.

Setup:

Candies type M&Ms

Instructions:

You must never say the words "arm wrestle." Here's what you do:

- Have everyone find a partner.
- Ask partners to "assume this position." Demonstrate with a volunteer, and hand link position with both of your elbows on the table.
- Explain, "This is a very easy exercise. There are two things you must know.
o1- you get a point if the back of your partner's hand touches the table
o2-you want to get as many points for yourself as possible. You don't care about anyone else.
- Explain, "Each 'point' is worth one candy/M&M. You will have only 10 seconds to get as many candies/ M&Ms as you can. GO.

Now for the debrief

- Poll the group: By a show of hands, ask how many points each person got. "0 points?" "1-5 points?" "6-20 points?" "More than 20?"
- Behavior questions: For a team that got a LOT of points, ask, "what did you do?" If everyone gets locked, ask "How did you lock? Why? Could you have done anything differently?" Offer to show how some teams generated many points: by either flip flopping their hands backward and forward or by repeatedly tapping one players hand on the table and agreeing to share the points.
- Reasoning questions: For pairs who got many points, ask how or why they did what they did. How did they come to that? Who said what to whom? What were you thinking? Did the person who came up with the idea offer tap the the back of their partners hand on the table, rather than their own?
- Assumptions questions: For teams that got very few points, try to tease out the assumptions they made that limited their success, such as:

- We've seen this game before
- We know how this game is played
- We assumed no communication
- We assumed we had to keep our hands together
- We didn't trust each other
- We assumed the rules were set.

Presentation of Negotiation (PowerPoint/Annex 3) Ugli Orange

Aim:

Simulation of a conflict situation. Participants will practice on conflict analysis and resolution by using negotiation skills.

Setup:

Handouts (Annex 4)

Instructions:

I. Background:

- We will now seek to highlight some of the basic principles of CPS by doing "The Ugli Orange Exercise".
- Is anyone familiar with it? If so, please be observers during the exercise.
- Everyone else, please count off by fours. Odd numbers to the left side of the room, even numbers to the right side. Left side = "Dr. Jones", Right side = "Dr. Roland".
- Read the following scenario:

Dr. Jones and Dr. Roland, two biological research scientists representing rival pharmaceutical companies, each seek to acquire the entire crop of Ugli Oranges that was grown in the world this year.

Dr. Jones is interested in the Ugli Oranges because of a recent outbreak of Rudosen, a disease contracted by pregnant women that causes serious brain, eye, and ear damage to unborn children unless the pregnant mothers are inoculated early in their pregnancies. The Ugli Orange can be made into a synthetic chemical serum by Dr. Jones' company to prevent the spread of Rudosen.

Dr. Roland is interested in the Ugli Oranges because of a recent leak of nerve gas from old chemical warfare bombs stored in bomb chambers on a small Pacific island. Thousands of people will die or suffer serious brain damage if the gas gets out of the bomb chambers and spreads to the coast. The Ugli Orange can be made into a synthetic chemical gas by Dr. Roland's company to neutralize the nerve gas.

Mr. Cardoza, a farmer in South America, owns most or all of the Ugli Oranges grown in the world this year.

You represent Dr. Jones (left side of room) and Dr. Roland (right side). After reading the instructions, you will have an opportunity to speak with each other to see if you can develop a joint proposal before going to South America to try to purchase the Ugli Oranges from Mr. Cardoza.

II. Confidential instructions:

[Hand out the “confidential instructions”- “Dr. Jones” to half of the participants and “Dr. Roland” to the other half.] These confidential instructions will give you more information for your role. [Give everyone 5 minutes to read.]

III. Negotiations:

Pair up each “Dr. Jones” with each “Dr. Roland.” Ask them to find a private space for their discussion and to return in 10 minutes for debriefing. (Use breakout rooms, if any are available.)

* Stop the simulation after 10 minutes.

IV Debriefing:

○ Did any group not come to an agreement? What were the problems?
○ Did any of the groups reach agreement? What were they? (There will be a rich mixture of experiences for the debriefing.) Some of the pairs may not have reached a solution. The remaining negotiated solutions fall into several different categories:

- Compromises in which they divide the oranges (usually 1/2 and 1/2, but sometimes 2/3 and 1/3).

- For pairs that discover that Dr. Roland wants only rinds and Dr. Jones wants only juice, they “expand the pie” and, in effect, get 6000 oranges.

○ For those who discovered the juice/rind secret: How did you find out?

○ Those of you who found that Dr. Roland needs the rind and Dr. Jones needs the juice, you were able to move beyond the position of “I need all of the oranges” to the interest, “I need the rinds/ juice of all of the oranges.”

○ Key concepts to discuss:

- The importance of understanding the difference between positions versus interests - inquiring and listening.

- The importance of effective two-way communication for conflict resolution.

- Usually, we argue for our positions and don't talk about our interests.

Close up (repeat/see above)

Wrap up/evaluation

Ask from participants to sit again in circle. Ask them to share one word they want, describing their experience from today's workshop. That one word can be a thought, a feelings etc.

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ANNEXES

Annex 1

Conflict-How Do You See It?

1. How do you define conflict?
2. What is your typical response to conflict?
3. What is your greatest strength when dealing with conflict?
4. If you could change one thing about the way you handle conflict, what would it be? Why?
5. What is the most important outcome of conflict?
6. In what ways have you seen your team benefit from conflict?
7. How can conflict be detrimental to a team?
8. What do you do when someone avoids conflict with you?
9. What are some reasons you choose to avoid conflict?

Annex 2

Assertiveness & Handouts Assertiveness

ASSERTIVENESS

Assertiveness is a way of communication. It describes being able to express your feelings, your thoughts, your beliefs and your views in an open manner, without violating the rights of others. It is the ability to honestly express your views and feelings without undue stress. Other ways of communication are the aggressive way, which violates the rights of others, and the passive way, which violates your own rights. You may have heard of the passive-aggressive way of communication. This occurs when someone is primarily aggressive but in a passive or indirect way. For example, someone might be angry, but they don't act in a visibly aggressive manner by shouting or beating. Instead, they sulk or slam the door.

PASSIVE WAY OF COMMUNICATION:
It violates our own rights. The needs of others come as priority.

ASSERTIVE WAY OF COMMUNICATION:
It respects my needs and the needs of others.

AGGRESSIVE WAY OF COMMUNICATION:
It violates the rights of others. My own needs come as priority.

THE OUTCOME OF NOT BEING ASSERTIVE

The main outcome is low self-esteem. If we choose to communicate in a passive way, we don't say what we really feel or think. This means that we may end up agreeing with the others and satisfying their needs or wishes rather than ours. This can result in a feeling that we do not have a destination or goal in our life and a sense that we cannot control our own lives. If we never openly express ourselves and we conceal our thoughts and feelings, this makes us feel tense, stressed and resentful. It often leads to unhealthy and uncomfortable relations. We feel that even our closest persons do not really know us.

HOW CAN I BECOME ASSERTIVE?

Assertiveness is an attitude and way of thinking that can be learnt. We are all born assertive. Think of babies. Babies cry when they want something, they freely express their feeling. Then gradually they adapt their behavior in order for it to match the responses they receive from their environment, which are responses received from their family, schoolmates, colleagues, superiors. For example, if your family or environment faced confrontation by shouting, then you will likely have learnt to deal with conflicts in this way. If your family taught you that you first have to satisfy others, before yourself, then you might find it difficult to claim your own needs. Or if your family taught you that you shouldn't express your negative emotions and ignored or laughed at you when you did so, then you very quickly learned not to express your negative emotion.

Some questions which may be useful to answer when you think about how you may have learnt not being assertive are:

How did your family handle confrontations?

What did they do when they disagreed with somebody or felt upset with people?

How did your parents teach you to handle confrontations?

What were their messages?

In what ways did you learn to get what you want without directly asking for it? (e.g. crying, shouting, threatening etc.)

Do you still use these ways to get what you want?

As you can see from the examples, there are often many good reasons why we did not become assertive. As children and teenagers we learnt to behave in ways which were effective for us at that time. If we were assertive to parents or aggressive friends, this would create problems for us and that is why we learned to hide ourselves and avoid. Or we learned to be aggressive in order to survive. And it is very likely that our family or our friends, from whom we learned this behavior, also learned this behavior from their own environment. It is very important to not blame myself or my family for the lack of assertiveness. It is much more useful and helpful to think of the above behavior as a vicious circle that you and your family were trapped in. Now you need to decide to break this vicious circle and to learn a new assertive way of thinking and behaving. This means that you won't convey this dysfunctional behavior to your future family and friends.

HOW ASSERTIVE AM I?

It is often difficult to know how assertive I am. In some cases we may feel capable of demanding, while in other situations we find ourselves not expressing what we really feel, which results in our feeling angry with ourselves. The following exercise can help you decide how assertive you are and it can also help you work on situations where you would like to be more assertive. On the left column we have a list of different situations demanding assertiveness. Then there are various groups of people. You can work column by column and mark any combination of situation and people.

RATING MY ASSERTIVENESS IN DIFFERENT SITUATIONS: Fill each cell using a scale of 0 -5. 0 means that you can claim for yourself without any problem. 5 means that you cannot claim for yourself at all.

	Friends of the same sex	Friends of the opposite sex	Persons of authority	Strangers	Colleagues	Close relationships or husband/wife	Shop assistants
I say NO							
I give compliments							
I express my opinion							
I seek help							
I express my anger							
I express love and affection							
I declare my rights and needs							
I give criticism							
I accept criticism							
I start and continue a conversation							

RECOGNISING THE DIFFERENCES BETWEEN PASSIVE, AGGRESSIVE AND ASSERTIVE WAY OF COMMUNICATION

It is very important to learn how to recognize the verbal and non-verbal characteristics of different communication modes. When you learn them, you will be able to recognize the passive, aggressive and assertive behavior in you and others. The first step in order to change a behavior is to recognize which parts of it need change. It may be that you can talk in an assertive way e.g. your verbal skills are assertive but your non-verbal communication is passive or contradicts your verbal communication. For example: If you say "I don't like it when you do this", which is an assertion statement, but you do it with a very quiet voice, without looking the other at the eyes, moving your legs, then your non-verbal communication undermines your verbal communication and your message will probably not be taken into serious consideration.

THE FEATURES OF PASSIVE COMMUNICATION DEFINITION:

I do not express my feelings, thoughts and beliefs with honesty. Therefore, I allow the others to violate my rights. It can also mean that I express my thoughts and feelings apologetically or in a style indifferent to myself, with the result that the others ignore what I communicate. I violate my rights

Sometimes I show an underlying lack of respect to the other's ability to accept disappointments, to undertake responsibilities or to handle their own problems.

VERBAL FEATURES:

Long and vague sentences.

I issue around without saying what I really mean.

Hesitant speech, full of pauses.

Frequent throat clearing.

I apologize for no apparent reason with soft and unsteady voice.

I use expressions of the type: "If it is not much trouble for you.."

I use additional words and expressions such as: "maybe" "um" "uh" "somehow"

My voice is boring and monotonous

The tone of my voice is tuneful or whining

I speak in a super-soft or super-warm way

Frequent excuses "Normally I would not have told you anything..."

Apologies “I am terribly sorry to bother you..”

I anticipate... “It is just my opinion....” or “I could be wrong....”

Self-rejection “It is not important” or “It doesn’t matter that much”

Self-criticism “You know me...” or “I am useless...desperate”

NON-VERBAL FEATURES:

Look that avoids

I look down

Retracted posture

I rub my hands

I close my eyes or laugh when I express my anger

I cover my mouth with my hand

I cross my arms for protection

I smile when I express anger or accept criticism

I raise eyebrows with a feeling of expectation

I move my chin

I bite my lips

WAYS OF THINKING:

“I do not count”

“My emotions, my needs and my thoughts are less important than yours”

“People will think bad things about me or they will not like me”

“If I say no, then someone may be upset, I will then be responsible for upsetting them”

BENEFITS

I am being praised for not being selfish.

I am rarely to blame when things do not go well because I usually have not taken the initiative.

The others will protect and take care of me.

I avoid, postpone or hide confrontations so that I feel a short-term stress reduction.

COSTS

Quite prone to accumulate stress and anger which can explode in a really offensive way.

The others make often unreasonable demands on me.

I limit myself to the image that the others have of me, the image of the good lovable person.

When I oppress my anger and frustration, other positive feelings I have in me are reduced.

Loss of self-esteem and self-respect.

PASSIVE BEHAVIOR FEATURES:

Passive behavior has to do with the fact that I don't express my feelings, my needs, my rights and my views.

Feelings: I choke on my own feeling or express them in indirect or non-helping ways.

Needs: I evaluate the needs of others as more important than my own needs. I constantly retreat to them all the time.

Rights: The other person has rights but you do not allow yourself to have the same privilege.

Views: You see yourself as having little or nothing to contribute, while you see the other as always being right. You might be afraid to tell what you think, in the possibility that your ideas are ridiculed.

THE PURPOSE OF THE PASSIVE BEHAVIOR IS TO ALWAYS AVOID CONFLICTS AND TO PLEASE THE OTHERS.

FEATURES OF AGGRESSIVE COMMUNICATION

DEFINITION:

I claim my rights and express my needs, thoughts and beliefs in a way which is inappropriate and always violates the rights of the other person.

People often feel overwhelmed after a confrontation with an aggressive person.

My superiority is maintained with underestimating others.

VERBAL FEATURES

Sharp, sarcastic or condescending voice

Eloquent. Few hesitations.

Often abrupt way of speaking

Often fast

With emphasis on blaming words

Steady voice

Cold and sarcastic tone

The voice can be intense, often loud, with increasing volume at the end of each sentence.

Use of threats "You better beware.." "If not..."

Disparaging remarks "You must be joking" "Don't be so stupid"

Evaluation of remarks. Emphasizing on concepts such as "should" "bad" "you have to"
Sexist or racist comments

I rant "I don't have problems like yours"

Views are expressed as facts "Nobody wants to behave in this way" "This is the useless way to do it..."

Threatening questions "Haven't you finished yet?" "Why the hell did you do it like that..."

NON-VERBAL FEATURES

Violation of the personal space of the other person

I look intensely

Gestures such as showing or clenching my fist

Walking with big steps impatiently

Leaning on or over (another)

Crossing my arms to show unapproachable

The smile can become derisory

I make wrinkles when I am angry

I clench my chins

WAYS OF THINKING

"I will catch you before you even have the chance to catch me"

"The world is a battlefield and I have to win"

BENEFITS

I get the others to do what I want

Things happen the way I want

I like the feeling of controlling

Relief of energy or tension

I feel strong

COSTS

My behavior creates hostility and resentment to those around me

This can lead to a sense of excessive fear and paranoia

If I always try to control the others, it is difficult for me to relax

My relationships are based on negative feelings and will be unstable

Aggressive persons actually feel inferior and they try to compensate this feeling by diminishing others.

Feelings of guilt and shame

Reduced self-confidence and self-esteem

FEATURES OF ASSERTIVE COMMUNICATION

DEFINITION:

A way to communicate my feelings, thoughts and needs in an open, honest manner, without violating the rights of others.

It is the alternative to being aggressive, which violates the rights of others, and to being passive, which violates my rights.

VERBAL FEATURES

Steady and stable voice

I am eloquent with few hesitations

Fixed rhythm of speaking

My tone is rich and warm

Honest and clear speech

Not strong neither low voice intensity

My voice is appropriately loud according to the circumstances

Statements using "I" "I like" "I want" "I do not like", which are short and to the point!

Phrases favoring cooperation "What are your thoughts on this?"

Emphatic declarations of interest "I would like to..."

Distinction between opinion and fact! "My experience is different..."

Sentences without "must" but with "How about..." or "Would you like to...?"

Constructive criticism without blaming "I feel annoyed when you interrupt me"

Seeking the views of the other "How does this fit with your idea...?"

Willingness to explore other solutions "How can we overcome the problem...?"

NON-VERBAL FEATURES

Receptive hearing

Good eye-contact

Upright, open posture

Pleasant but serious facial expression

Open hands

I smile when I am happy

I frown when I am angry

My chin is relaxed

WAY OF THINKING

"I will not allow you to take advantage of me and I will not attack you for who you are"

BENEFITS

The more I respect myself and I act in a respecting way, the greater my self-esteem

The opportunities to get what I want from life are improved.

Expressing what I feel the moment that I feel it, doesn't mean that I don't cultivate resentment in me.

If I am driven less by my need to protect myself and I am less busy with my self-conscience, then I can listen to the others and love them more easily.

COSTS

My friends and/or my family may have benefited from me being passive and they can sabotage or complicate this new behavior of mine.

I reshape beliefs that I had built in my childhood and it looks frightening

It doesn't mean that by claiming I always get I want.

At first my attempt is difficult.

ASSERTIVENESS TECHNIQUES

BASIC ASSERTIVENESS

Basic assertiveness is when we make a statement that clearly expresses our needs, desires, beliefs, opinions and feelings. This kind of assertiveness can be daily used with the aim to inform about our needs. Basic rules: Use of first person (I, me...)

e.g.: "I need to be there by 5"

"I feel satisfied with how the issue was solved"

You can also use basic assertiveness to make compliments or praise someone, give information or when an issue arises with someone for the first time.

e.g.: "I have never thought of this in the past, I would like to consider your idea" "I believe that your presentation was very good" "The price will be 200 euros" "I like it when you help me"

It is important to remember to be specific when you make your statements. Decide what it is that you want or feel and say it concretely or directly. Avoid unnecessary "fillings" and keep your statement simple and short. This skill will help you to be clear about what you wish to communicate. Basic assertiveness also includes the so called "self-revelation". It essentially means disclosing my feelings with a simple statement. For example: "I feel nervous" "I feel guilty" "I feel angry". The immediate effect of this technique is that your stress is reduced, allowing you to relax and take responsibility of yourself and your feelings. Using the first person "I etc." to express your feelings, also shows that you take responsibility for your own feelings.

EMPATHETIC ASSERTIVENESS

Empathy means that we try to understand the feelings, needs and desires of the other person. So, this type of assertiveness includes elements of recognition of the other person's needs and at the same time, a statement of your own needs and feelings. This kind of assertiveness can be used when the other person is involved in a situation which might not fit with your needs, and you want to state that you are aware of this and you are sensitive about his/her position.

EXAMPLES:

"I understand that you don't like the new procedure, however, until it changes, I would like you to keep working on this"

"John, I know you are busy right now, but I would like to ask you something"

"I recognize it is difficult to be precise about the cost, but I need a rough estimate"

Empathetic assertiveness is useful in protecting you from aggressively overreacting, as it gives you time to imagine yourself in the other person's position and therefore, delay your response. It is highly likely that you over-use specific statements in empathetic assertiveness, and this will result in your statement seeming false. Moreover, your statement might seem as covert aggressiveness. For example, if someone says "I appreciate your feelings but..." then the empathetic statement "I appreciate your feelings" is underestimated by the word "but" and the phrase becomes a covert offensive.

ASSERTIVENESS OF CONSEQUENCE

This is the strongest type of assertiveness and we see it as a last option, when someone does not take into account the rights of the others and you want to change their behavior without becoming aggressive as well. It can be used at work when procedures or directions are not properly followed. When using an assertive behavior of consequence, you inform the other person about the consequences that will occur if they don't change their behavior. It can very easily be perceived as a threat and hence, as aggressiveness. Use this type of assertiveness when you have sanctions to impose and only when you are ready to implement them. As this type of assertiveness may be perceived as aggressive, you need to be careful with the non-verbal signs you use. Keep your voice calm, with steady volume, having good eye contact and trying to have your face and body relaxed.

EXAMPLES

"If you continue withholding information, I will have no other choice left but to report this to the director. I would rather not do that".

"If this happens again, I will have no other choice left but to implement the formal disciplinary procedure, I would rather not do that".

ASSERTIVENESS OF DISAGREEMENT

This type works with showing the discrepancy between what was agreed and what is really happening. This technique is useful when there is a misunderstanding or contradiction, and one's behavior does not match their words.

EXAMPLES

"As I understood, we agreed that project 1 would be our first priority. Now you are asking me more time for project 2. I would like to clarify what is now our priority".

"George, on the one hand you tell me that you want to develop cooperation between the two sectors, on the other hand you make statements about us that make it difficult for us to work with you. I agree that we can improve the situation, that is why I wanted us to talk about it".

ASSERTIVENESS OF NEGATIVE FEELINGS

This kind of technique is used when experiencing very negative feelings towards another person - anger, resentment etc. With a controlled and calm manner, you focus your attention on the adverse effect that the other person's behavior has on you. This allows you to handle your feelings without an uncontrolled outburst. It also alerts the other person about the consequences of their actions on you.

THERE ARE 4 STEPS FOR VINDICATING NEGATIVE FEELINGS:

- 1 Describe the other person's behavior objectively. Be careful to do that without interpreting or judging. "When you leave it until the last minute to do your job..."
- 2 Describe the impact of the other person's behavior on you. Be precise and clear. Do not over-generalize. "It affects the work I have to do during the weekend".
- 3 Describe your feeling "I feel annoyed with this"
- 4 State how you would prefer this behavior to be in the future "From now on I would like to have everything delivered by Tuesday noon".

OTHER EXAMPLES:

"When you come home late without having informed me in advance, I am worried that something is wrong and I am angry. I would really appreciate it if you could call me and inform me in advance"

"When you constantly interrupt me while I am working on this task, it means I have to do everything again from scratch. That is why I would rather you waited until I finish what I have to do"

"STUCK NEEDLE" TECHNIQUE

Kids are experts in this technique. This skill includes preparing what you aim to do and repeating it as often as you deem necessary, in a calm way. This skill can be used under most circumstances. It is a good skill to use when you have to deal with smart people, as the only thing you have to do is be persistent on your prepared quotes. It helps you stay relaxed as you know what you are about to say and you can keep a constant statement avoiding irrelevant logical or argumentative pitfalls. It is a good technique to say no.

EXAMPLE:

-May I borrow 20 euros from you?

-I cannot lend you now. I am completely broke.

-I will give them back as soon as I can. I need them very much. You are my friend, right?

-I cannot lend you anything at all.

-I would do the same for you. You won't miss 20 euros.

-I am your friend but I cannot lend you money. I am completely broke.

This technique can be easily combined with other techniques just learned above. Always start with the calmest attitude. Then become more and more assertive. Avoid jumping directly to the attitude with the most severe consequences. It would be a threatening and aggressive behavior and not an assertive one.

The following "stuck needle" example uses all levels of assertiveness, starting with the basic assertiveness, then passing to the empathetic one, and lastly, to the assertiveness of consequence.

BASIC

"I bought this watch from here yesterday. The button setting the indicators does not function properly and I would like to change it"

At this point the seller either agrees either:

"You should have checked this watch before leaving the store"

EMPATHY

"I understand this would make things easier, however I would like to replace it"

At this point the seller either agrees either:

"It does not fall under my duties to change products"

AFTER A LOT OF ANTI-PROPOSALS, THE LEVEL COULD INCREASE

CONSEQUENCE

"I would like to replace this product. If you are not willing to do this, I will refer the issue to the supervisor. I would prefer to have the issue resolved now"

The only situation where this technique would be deficient is when you ask something from someone who does not want to do it. When they keep denying, your demand loses its power every time it is repeated. In cases like these, it is necessary to have consequences.

All these techniques need practice. Start with the basic assertiveness and practice for one-two weeks before starting with the other techniques.

RULES OF ASSERTIVENESS

I HAVE THE RIGHT TO:

- 1 Respect myself- what I am and what I do
- 2 Recognize my needs as an autonomous being-this is different from what the others expect from me, depending on my role each time as a "daughter", "student" "brother" etc.
- 3 I use clear statements with "I". About how I feel and what I believe. I focus on the problem that I have without blaming the other. e.g. "I would like to be able to tell my stories without interruptions" instead of "You constantly interrupt me!"
- 4 I allow myself to make mistakes. Recognizing that making mistakes is absolutely normal.
- 5 I change my mind if I want to
- 6 I ask to "think about it for a while" e.g. When someone asks me to do something, I have the right to say "I would like to think about it for a while and I will inform you of my decision by the end of the week".
- 7 I allow myself to enjoy my happiness, this means being happy and satisfied with what I have achieved and sharing it with those around me
- 8 I ask what I want-rather than hoping that the other will observe what it is that I want
- 9 I recognize that I am not responsible for the conduct of other adults
- 10 I respect the other persons and their right to be assertive and I expect the same for me.

SOME FINAL REMARKS

One of the most common problems in our communication with others is caused by our attempt to read the minds of others or our anticipation that the others will read our minds. If you want people to respond to your ideas and needs, you have to be able to say what these are and say it in a manner that makes the others wanting to respond in a nice way. The rationale is self-efficiency. The belief that if I do something in a certain way, I will be efficient. A sense that if I behave in a certain way, something which I can predict will happen. Even if now you don't believe this, using the rules of assertive behavior and communication, the results will be so promising that you will start to believe in your efficiency. If it is scary for you to think being assertive, try it first to people you don't know. Bring to your mind someone you know that is assertive and pretend that you are this person. People feel it when you respect yourself and they will also treat you with respect. This is the ultimate goal of assertive communication.

Handouts Assertiveness

RATE THE FOLLOWING STATEMENTS

1 NEVER 2 SELDOM 3 SOMETIMES 4 USUALLY 5 ALWAYS

- 1 I can say «no» to very persistent salesmen
- 2 I can return defective products I have bought to the store.....
- 3 I can express my feelings when someone is taking my place in line
- 4 I can listen to someone's criticism when they say I am doing something in a wrong way without being defensive and without getting upset
- 5 I can talk in front of a group of people without great amount of stress
- 6 I can complain about unreasonable work load
- 7 I can retain my opinion whenever I am facing an aggressive or stubborn Person
- 8 I can negotiate my salary raise and changes within my work environment
- 9 I can ask questions or ask for information without being afraid of seem stupid or incapable
- 10 I can take a stand whenever I fell something is unfair for me
- 11 I can stand up for my rights when a person with high status is behaving in an irrational way or they are rude
- 12 I can insist that the owner of my house should handle to fix something or replace something in the house
- 13 I can ask for money or things that I have borrowed back, without having apologetic attitude
- 14 Whenever I need help or favor from a friend, I can ask it directly from them without using indirect ways in asking what I want
- 15 I can get close to people and start a friendly relationship
- 16 I can deny to do something that I do not want to do without feeling guilty
- 17 I can express my affection and love in an open way
- 18 I can ask from my roommate/husband/wife to share the household chores.....
- 19 I can say NO to close friends/relatives requests when they ask from me to do things in the way they want them to do it
- 20 When someone does something that bothers me, I can express my feelings about it
- 21 I can accept a compliment without devaluated it in my mind
- 22 I can accept my own mistakes and flaws
- 23 I can make my own decisions and feel good about them
- 24 I am/will be a good example of assertiveness for my child

Annex 3

Negotiation plays a major role in all aspects of our professional and personal life.

Any discussion that requires a decision at some level with an expected or unexpected outcome involves and requires negotiating skills.

Elements of Successful negotiation

- Preparation
- Effective Communication Skills
- Emotional Control
- Closing the deal

Preparation: Most important element to a successful outcome. Includes identifying the intended goal as well as setting limits to achieve that goal.

- ▶ Developing a position of strength
- ▶ Establishing a foundation for success and developing confidence
- ▶ Setting goals
- ▶ Defining and Setting limits

Communication Skills

- Successful Communication
- Active Listening
- Clarity
 - Ask questions that can help to identify keys issues of the discussion
 - Use the information that was required during pre-negotiation preparation to formulate questions that can narrow the issues of discussion

- Use appropriate terminology to facilitate an accurate understanding of the issues being discussed.
- Follow-up questions that will require a more specific answer when responses are too general
- Keep responses short and very specific to the questions. Avoid inserting information that may be interesting but not necessarily specific to the subject
- Body language

Emotional Control

- Emotional control = Emotional Distance

Emotional control begins by understanding our own personal strengths and weaknesses. Emotional control may necessitate emotional distance to neutralize the situation and avoid further conflict

- Difficult People

Rather than excluding a person, try to draw him into the process by encouraging constructive ideas and suggestions.

Final Negotiations–Closing the deal

A “win-win” outcome is based on the subjective perception of a “win” as defined in the initial goals established during the preparation process. A win-win is achieved through honesty and respect from both parties.

Closing a deal is not always possible.

Final tips

- Empathy
- Flexibility
- Patience
- Stamina
- Responsibility
- Fairness
- Self discipline
- Respect
- Personal Integrity
- Sense of Humor

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Annex 4

Confidential Instructions DR. JONES

UGLI ORANGE

You are Dr. Jones, a biological research scientist employed by a pharmaceutical company. You have recently developed a synthetic chemical useful for curing and preventing Rudosen, a disease contracted by pregnant women. If not caught in the first four weeks of pregnancy, the disease causes serious brain, eye, and ear damage to the unborn child. Recently, there has been an outbreak of Rudosen in your country and several thousand women have contracted the disease. You have found, with volunteer victims, that your recently developed synthetic serum cures Rudosen in its early stages. Unfortunately, the serum is made from the Ugli orange which is a very rare fruit. Only about 4,000 of these oranges were grown in the whole world this season. No additional Ugli oranges will be available until next season, which will be too late to cure the present Rudosen victims.

You have demonstrated that your synthetic serum does no harm to the pregnant women. There are no side effects. Unfortunately, the present outbreak of Rudosen was unexpected and your company had not planned on having the serum available for six months. Your company holds the patent on the synthetic serum and it is expected to be a highly profitable product when it is generally available to the public.

You have recently been told a Mr. Cardoza, a South American fruit exporter, has 3,000 Ugli oranges. If you could obtain all 3,000 of these Ugli oranges, you could make enough serum from the juice of these oranges to both cure all the present victims and provide sufficient inoculation for the remaining pregnant women in your country. No other country currently has a Rudosen threat.

You have been told that Dr. Roland is also urgently seeking Ugli oranges and is also aware that Cardoza has some of these special oranges. Dr. Roland is employed by a competing pharmaceutical company. Roland has been working on biological warfare research for the past several years. There is a great deal of industrial espionage in the pharmaceutical industry. Over the past several years, Dr. Roland's company and your company have sued each other for infringement of patent rights and espionage law violations several times.

You've been authorized by your company to approach Cardoza to purchase the 3,000 Ugli oranges. You have been told Cardoza will sell them to the highest bidder. Your company has authorized you to bid as high as \$250,000 (USD) to obtain the juice of the 3,000 available oranges.

Before approaching Cardoza, you have decided to talk with Dr. Roland. Think carefully about what information you are willing to tell the other side, and what information you will not disclose.

Confidential Instructions

DR. ROLAND

UGLI ORANGE

You are Dr. Roland, a research biologist for a pharmaceutical company. Your company has a government contract to do research on methods to combat enemy uses of biological warfare, but the government has asked your company for assistance with an immediate problem.

Recently, several old experimental nerve gas bombs were moved to a small Pacific island. While they were being moved, two of the bombs developed leaks. The leaks are presently controlled, but government scientists believe that within two weeks the gas will leak out of bomb chambers and escape. There is no known method of preventing the gas from getting into the atmosphere and spreading to the coast. If the leak occurs, several thousands of people will die or incur serious brain damage.

You have developed a synthetic vapor that will neutralize the nerve gas if it is injected into the bomb chamber before the gas leaks out. The vapor is made with a chemical taken from the Ugli orange, a very rare fruit.

You've heard that a Mr. Cardoza, a fruit exporter in South America, has 3,000 Ugli oranges. If you get all 3,000 Ugli Oranges you could make enough of the chemical from the rind these oranges to neutralize all of the gas if the serum is developed and injected efficiently. Your company has not been able to locate any more of these Ugli oranges. As far as you know, there are only 3,000 such oranges in the world crop this year.

You have learned that Dr. Jones is also urgently seeking to purchase Ugli oranges and that Jones is aware that Cardoza has oranges available. Dr. Jones' company and your company are highly competitive, and there is a great deal of industrial espionage in the pharmaceutical industry. Your company and Dr. Jones' company have sued each other twice for infringement of patent rights. One law suit is still going on.

You've been authorized by your company to approach Cardoza to purchase the 3,000 Ugli oranges. You have been told that Cardoza will sell them to the highest bidder. Your company has authorized you to bid as high as \$250,000 (USD) to obtain the oranges.

Before approaching Cardoza, you have decided to talk to Dr. Jones. Think carefully about what information you are willing to tell the other side, and what information you will not disclose.

MODULE 3: MY PLAN

(Duration 3hours)

DESCRIPTION OF MODULE:

Time management is an important soft skill for individuals in order to keep a balance between work and personal life. People who feel that are able to organize time and activities they refer less stress and higher quality of life. According to salutogenesis people who have a sense of coherence (a fundamental concept for salutogenesis) show manageability namely they are able to manage/control their life events and find the required resources to face problems.

It is necessary to see time management as a multidimensional concept because (a) it is easier to understand its mechanism and the different aspects you have to work on (b) it gives you the opportunity to realize how different aspects of time management relate to salutogenesis. For example dealing with priorities can be seen under the light of meaningfulness element of sense of coherence, in other words someone's ability to appraise some situations as meaningful and others as not significant.

Setting goals and find meaningful life aims is also associated with the sense of coherence concept of salutogenic model and is considered as health promoting factor.

Self-evaluation is also a concept related to salutogenesis. Self-evaluation is connected with someone's ability to participate in the decision-making process. People who participate in a decision-making process can create conditions in which they can build a strong sense of coherence.

MODULE TOPICS:

- Time Management
- Prioritizing
- Goal Setting
- Procrastination

CONTENTS OF TRAINING INTERVENTION

ICEBREAKER AND NAME GAMES

TIME MANAGEMENT

“Time to invest”

Aim:

A quick group activity that highlights the importance of planning and prioritizing to manage time properly.

Setup:

Several fake blank checks of \$86,400 each/flipchart paper/pens.

Instructions:

- Split the class into 3 or 4 teams.
- Issue one check to each team and tell them that they have 24 hours to spend the total amount written on the check.
- Using a flip chart, each team has to plan exactly how they will spend the \$86,400 to the penny, any amount left that they fail to plan for will be taken away from them.
- Give the teams 15 minutes to start their plans and once done, each team's spokesperson has to present their plan.

Discussion points:

Lead discussion about how good each plan is and how each team made sure every penny was well spent. Make the point that each day we all get the same amount in minutes. Each day we are issued a check for 86,400 minutes but do we plan it that wisely? Link back to the importance of prioritizing and planning to properly manage time.

PRESENTATION POWERPOINT “Introduction of Theory” (Annex 1)

“Bucket List”

Aim:

To create material for future exercise

Setup:

A4/pens

Instructions:

Ask participants to write out 10 items that are on their “bucket list.” A “bucket list” is a list of things that we want to do before we die (or “kick the bucket”). Bucket list items can be large or small. Encourage them to daydream a little, and not let lack of money, time, or permission to restrict their ideas. Just write the list.

Debrief by asking the group to look at their list. Now that they have a list of what they really want, they will have some ideas about what they need to change in order to get where they want to go. Encourage them to keep this list in mind as they go through the workshop.

PRESENTATION "TIME MANAGEMENT" (Annex 1)

Urgency vs. Importance Trap

It is important to understand where you are spending most of your time and if you acknowledge that time is being wasted or you are spending time on less productive things, think of methods to overcome this. Some people argue that some comfort activities like playing games or chatting are useful to them and they do not feel that they should stop them as it helps to recharge their batteries. The simple question is, 'Is that activity important to you then?', if it is, then it goes into the important, but not urgent box!

Look at the following and consider whether or not you agree with it. Consider the following categorisation:

	Urgent	Not Urgent
Important	<p>1 DO NOW</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> emergencies, complaints, crisis issues demands from bosses or customers planned tasks or project work now due meetings and appointments reports and other submissions staff issues or needs problem resolution, fire-fighting, fixes <p>Subject to confirming the importance and the urgency of these tasks, do these tasks now. Prioritise according to their relative urgency.</p>	<p>2 PLAN TO DO</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> planning, preparation, scheduling research, investigation, designing, testing networking, relationship building thinking, creating, modelling, designing systems and process development anticipation and prevention developing change, direction, strategy <p>Critical to success: planning, strategic thinking, deciding direction and aims, etc. Plan time-slots and personal space for these tasks.</p>
Not Important	<p>3 REJECT AND EXPLAIN</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> trivial requests from others apparent emergencies ad-hoc interruptions, distractions misunderstandings appearing as complaints pointless routines or activities accumulated unresolved trivia <p>Scrutinise and probe demands. Help originators to re-assess. Wherever possible reject and avoid these tasks sensitively and immediately.</p>	<p>4 RESIST AND CEASE</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 'comfort' activities, computer games, net surfing, excessive breaks chat, gossip, social communications daydreaming, doodling, reading irrelevant materials <p>Habitual 'comforters' not true tasks. Non-productive, de-motivational. Minimise or cease altogether. Plan to avoid them.</p>

The **URGENCY** of a task is determined by when it should be done - a task becomes more **URGENT** as the deadline for its completion approaches. The **IMPORTANCE** of a task is determined by its contribution to the achievement of key results and long term goals. Good time management involves identifying the urgency or lack of urgency and the importance or unimportance of tasks and planning accordingly. A useful tool for assessing urgency and importance is the Time Management Matrix. All tasks performed will fall into one of four categories on the Time Management Matrix depending on their urgency and importance as demonstrated by the illustration above. When we are not in full control of our activities, we tend to spend most of our time in box 1, the emergency zone. This highly stressed environment is not a healthy place to spend too much time in. Everything in this box is rushed and hurried and can become stressful. Examples of urgent, but not really important tasks include, quick and simple tasks and dealing with interruptions. To the interrupter it may seem important, but this doesn't necessarily mean it is important to you. If you spend too much time dealing with tasks that are important to others, you don't have enough time to allocate to your own important activities. We want to try minimise the time spent in this box as it adds little value to your key result areas and personal objectives.

Sometimes we find ourselves doing things that are not urgent and not important, things that we like doing or get a sense of comfort from, like photocopying. There is something to be said for doing things we enjoy that are unimportant, but only occasionally. We should aim to spend most of our time in box 2. In other words we work on high priority tasks that relate to our goals in plenty of time to manage the deadlines. We aim to operate as follows:

PRIORITIZING

“Prioritizing Exercise”

Aim:

To practice prioritizing skills

Setup:

Handout (Annex 2)/pens.

Instructions:

Prioritise the tasks by writing the corresponding letter in the correct box:

- a) Dealing with an angry complaint from one of your clients.
- b) Responding to a colleague who has just boiled the kettle and needs a quick answer as to whether you want tea or coffee.
- c) Writing a complex report requested by your boss (who is a good boss) that needs to be ready in three weeks' time.
- d) Dealing with a colleague who has interrupted you to get some information for a report she/he needs to deliver tomorrow. Completing the report does not progress your own objectives.
- e) Filing documents that you will need again later in the year to help achieve one of your key objectives.
- f) Improving the presentation of a routine straightforward report of limited circulation by adding colour, shading and clip art.
- g) You need to supply figures for an important meeting that has been called at short notice.
- h) The phone rings and you need to answer it.

Is this how you would normally undertake these tasks?

GOAL SETTING

“Target”

Aim:

Understand the concept and terms of goal setting

Setup:

Flipchart/marker

Instructions:

Draw a black dot in the center of a clean piece of flip chart paper and ask the group what it is. Answers may include a spot, a black dot, and an eye. Then draw a large circle around the black dot. Now ask the group what they think it is. Many of them will now say it's a target, or a bull's eye. Tell them that is correct.

Now ask for a volunteer. Have them come to the front and give them a small ball or a crumpled piece of paper. Ask them to turn around with their back to the target and try to hit it by throwing the paper or ball over his/her shoulder. When the student misses, as they most surely will, ask them and the group why they missed. They will probably say it's because the person couldn't see the target.

Debrief:

Most of us can't hit a target if we can't see it. Before you can develop plans, you have to know what you want to accomplish (your goals or targets); how you want to accomplish those goals or targets; what resources of time, money, and materials you have; and who will carry out the implementation. So set some targets for yourself, targets that you can see, and we'll start the journey to reaching them.

PRESENTATION OF THEORY-S.M.A.R.T (Annex 1)

"S.M.A.R.T goals"

Aim:

To learn the process of SMART goal setting.
To practice skills of goals clarification.

Setup:

Bucket List form previous exercise/A4/pens.

Instructions:

Look at your Bucket List
Select your most important goals (work and personal)
Write them as SMART goals
Write the key tasks associated with each goal

"Prioritizing and Planning"

Aim:

To familiarize themselves with process of prioritizing.

Setup:

2 Handouts Annex 3

Instructions:

Prioritising your tasks in accordance with the four categories is the first step in planning your time. You'll need to make a to-do list.
Take the Handout 1 and fill the form.

- Begin by putting down all your tasks and activities by goal.
 - Then give them a priority rating from 1-4 depending on their degree of importance and urgency.
 - Having prioritised each task, you then need to rank them in the order they need to be tackled. If you have trouble ranking the items as you feel they are all important and urgent ask yourself one question. "If I could only do one of these things which would it be?" This will help you decide on the highest ranking.
- Once the tasks have been prioritised and ranked, the next steps are estimating the time it will take to complete each task and scheduling the time to work on the tasks.

- When estimating time for a task the general approach is to estimate the duration in Pure Time i.e. the time it would take to complete the task without interruption.
- If we can really, genuinely allocate uninterrupted time, then this is fine, however, for the most part we generally operate in an environment of frequent disturbance and disruption. Consider adding an additional 25% to your calculations in order to realise the Actual Time.

When this is completed we can commence scheduling. When scheduling you need to be aware of Prime time and Down time. We all have different times of the day when we are at our peak. Some are larks, at their peak at the start of the day. Some people are not at their best early in the morning and need a couple of cups of coffee before they feel at their best. Others start the day well, but then tail off in the afternoon. Others are owls, at their best when evening approaches. It is important to recognise these periods and adjust your workload accordingly. At your prime time you should tackle complex tasks and save routine tasks for your down times.

HANDOUT 2:

Make a note in the following boxes of when your own prime and down times occur; then from your list of tasks, consider which tasks and activities you would be best doing at these times.

PROCRASTINATION

"Group Discussion-Procrastination"

Aim:

To exchange ideas about reasons for procrastination

To learn effective anti-procrastination strategies

Setup:

Handout (Annex 4)

Instructions:

Handout notes and discuss with the group in circle.

WRAP UP/EVALUATION

Ask from participants to sit again in circle. Ask them to share one word they want, describing their experience from today's workshop. That one word can be a thought, a feelings etc.

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ANNEXES

Annex 1 (PowerPoint)

Coping approaches conceive the problem of stress to be linked to the absence of a skill necessary for the dealing with the variety of upheavals, changes and demands that life imposes (Dhaniram, 2003).

Time management—generally defined as clusters of skills and behaviours that facilitate productivity and alleviate stress (Lay and Schouwenburg, 1993)—is one example of skills intervention training and is the focus of this module. In this module, time management is considered a multidimensional concept comprising goal and priority setting, use of time management mechanisms including planning and scheduling, organisation and perceived control of time (Macan, 1994).

ACTIVITY

Bucket List

What is Time Management?

Mesacn (1994) tells that is considered a multidimensional concept comprising:

Goal Setting:

The setting of goals concerning what a person wants or needs to accomplish and the prioritising of the tasks necessary to achieve these goals

I set goals for what I need to accomplish; I finish high priority tasks first

Mechanisms for time management:

The behaviours associates with managing time; making lists, scheduling and planning.

I schedule activities in advance

Organisation:

A general organised approach to work and the maintenance of an organised work environment

At the end of a work day I leave a clear well organised workspace; I can find things more easily than when my work space is disorganised.

Practically, effective time management involves developing processes and tools that increase efficiency and productivity.

Effectively assessing your tasks

Understanding how to assess your tasks according to their urgency and importance (e.g. Using tools such as the Time Management Matrix)

Scheduling priorities

Scheduling those activities on which an order of importance has been placed to ensure they get completed, e.g. completing a piece of instructional design, dealing with a student problem, selling your programmes

Scheduling routine activities

Scheduling day to day activities that are routine in nature, of which you have prior knowledge, e.g. work activities such as updating your financial records, regular networking meeting, professional development programme attendance, checking email, reviewing and updating student handbooks.

Establishing deadlines

Setting deadlines for tasks to ensure they get done by the time required

Scheduling routine activities

Scheduling day to day activities that are routine in nature, of which you have prior knowledge, e.g. work activities such as updating your financial records, regular networking meeting, professional development programme attendance, checking email, reviewing and updating student handbooks.

Establishing deadlines

Setting deadlines for tasks to ensure they get done by the time required

It is important to understand where you are spending most of your time and if you acknowledge that time is being wasted or you are spending time on less productive things, think of methods to overcome this. Some people argue that some comfort activities like playing games or chatting are useful to them and they do not feel that they should stop them as it helps to recharge their batteries. The simple question is, 'Is that activity important to you then?', if it is, then it goes into the important, but not urgent box!

		Urgent	Not Urgent	
Important	1 DO NOW	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> emergencies, complaints, crisis issues demands from bosses or customers planned tasks or project work now due meetings and appointments reports and other submissions staff issues or needs problem resolution, fire-fighting, fixes <p>Subject to confirming the importance and the urgency of these tasks, do these tasks now. Prioritize according to their relative urgency.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> planning, preparation, scheduling research, investigation, designing, testing networking, relationship building thinking, creating, modelling, designing systems and process development anticipation and prevention developing change, direction, strategy <p>Critical to success: planning, strategic thinking, deciding direction and aims, etc. Plan time-slots and personal space for these tasks.</p>	
	Not Important	3 REJECT AND EXPLAIN	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> trivial requests from others apparent emergencies ad-hoc interruptions, distractions misunderstandings appearing as complaints pointless routines or activities accumulated unresolved trivia <p>Scrutinise and probe demands. Help originators to re-assess. Whenever possible reject and avoid these tasks sensitively and immediately.</p>	4 RESIST AND CEASE

		Urgent	Not Urgent	
Important	1	 Minimise time spent here	 Maximise the time spent here	
	Not Important	3	 Effort spent here is of little value	4

Activity Prioritizing

Prioritise the tasks by writing the corresponding letter in the correct box:

- Dealing with an angry complaint from one of your client.
- Responding to a colleague who has just boiled the kettle and needs a quick answer as to whether you want tea or coffee.
- Writing a complex report requested by your boss (who is a good boss) that needs to be ready in three weeks' time.
- Dealing with a colleague who has interrupted you to get some information for a report she/he needs to deliver tomorrow. Completing the report does not progress your own objectives.

-Filing documents that you will need again later in the year to help achieve one of your key objectives.

-Improving the presentation of a routine straightforward report of limited circulation by adding colour, shading and clip art.

-You need to supply figures for an important meeting that has been called at short notice.

-The phone rings and you need to answer it.

Activity

“Target”

Most of us can't hit a target if we can't see it. Before you can develop plans, you have to know what you want to accomplish (your goals or targets); how you want to accomplish those goals or targets; what resources of time, money, and materials you have; and who will carry out the implementation.

So set some targets for yourself, targets that you can see, and we'll start the journey to reaching them.

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A goal or objective consists of a projected state of affairs which a person or a system plans or intends to achieve or bring about. "Goals provide a sense of direction and purpose", (Goldstein, 1993, p. 96). They encourage positive, focused action towards achieving success as it is defined by the goal and lessens the likelihood diversion to other non-essential activities that have the potential to hinder progress towards the achievement of the goal. Locke et al. (1981) on examining the behavioural effects of goal-setting concluded that 90% of laboratory and field studies involving specific and challenging goals led to higher performance than easy or no goals.

Goals should be well clarified. They should be Specific, Measurable, Realistic and Time Based.

GOALS

S pecific
M easurable
A ttainable
R ealistic
T ime based

Change From...

To be fit

To update courseware

To communicate better with my team

To learn to speak Spanish

To learn about computers

Change to...

To lower body weight by 3kg and be able to swim 50 lengths of the swimming pool at the local gym by 4th December.

To have revised and updates to course for two programmes the end of Q3.

To schedule and run monthly team briefings and quarterly one-to-one feedback meetings.

To understand what is being said and to speak in Spanish at the education conference in Madrid on November 16th.

To complete a Computer Basics Programme by December 15th.

ACTIVITY: S.M.A.R.T GOALS

Look at your **Bucket List**

Select your most important goals (work and personal)

Write them as SMART goals

Write the key tasks associated with each goal

ACTIVITY: Prioritizing and Planning

Prioritising your tasks in accordance with the four categories is the first step in planning your time. You'll need to make a to-do list.

Goal:	Zone	Ranking	Time
Task			

PROCRASTINATION

**Emotional difficulties that lead to/stem
from procrastination:**

- **LOW SELF-ESTEEM.**
- **LOW FRUSTRATION TOLERANCE.**
- **HOSTILITY**

Anti-procrastination Strategies

- ✓ First, schedule your tasks for your project.
- Second, take action!
- Third, use your friends
- Fourth, keep a journal!

Theory S.M.A.R.T

A goal or objective consists of a projected state of affairs which a person or a system plans or intends to achieve or bring about. "Goals provide a sense of direction and purpose", (Goldstein, 1993, p. 96). They encourage positive, focused action towards achieving success as it is defined by the goal and lessens the likelihood diversion to other non-essential activities that have the potential to hinder progress towards the achievement of the goal. Locke et al. (1981) on examining the behavioural effects of goal-setting concluded that 90% of laboratory and field studies involving specific and challenging goals led to higher performance than easy or no goals.

Well defined goals are Specific, Measurable, Attainable (Agreed is often used in an organisational setting), Realistic and Responsible, Time-framed and Trackable (Doran 1981). Goals should be Specific in detail without generalisations or lack of definition. They are best if they are Measurable and their progress is quantifiable so that clients know at any point where they are on the path to achieving their goal - they should also know when they have achieved it. Attainability is important too since if a goal is not attainable, it is de-motivating as there is no hope for success. This does not mean that challenging goals should not be set. A goal that doesn't challenge is also de-motivating. Agreed is often substituted here in organisational settings where the buy-in of a number of stakeholders is required. Without agreement there is the potential for misunderstanding and misinterpretation, loss of ownership and responsibility, and overall reduced performance.

Goals should also be Realistic in terms of the clients existing life situation, clients must be willing and able to undertake the work towards achieving their goals and the goals are Responsible and ecologically good for anybody concerned. Timed, Tangible and Trackable essentially means having a schedule and ongoing evidence of progress. Without a timeframe there is the potential for a lack of urgency, and activity on achieving the goal will simply drift. With a timeframe, you can keep track of your progress towards your goal, know where you are on the path to achieving your goal assess whether or not deviations have occurred and if corrective action is required to get back on track.

Goal setting also requires motivation. Simply setting a goal may lead to progress in the desired direction, but understanding why the targeted outcome of the goal is desired encourages personal investment into the achievement of the goal. The secret is to attain an understanding and create a compelling vision of the future to buy into. This goes beyond the purely technical which may fail to excite or enthuse (and in organizations, goals more often than not, simply disappear into the annual appraisal system) to the creation and visualisation of a desired future, eliciting a future-focused and detailed description of how things are in the future when they are successful, which makes the goal more Tangible and its achievement more desirable.

Annex 2
(Prioritizing Activity/Table)

	Urgent	Not urgent
Important	1	2
Not important	3	4

Annex 3
(Prioritizing and Planning)

Goal			
Activity	Time Zone	Rating	Duration

Handout: Prime Time and Down Time Exercise

Please complete in the following table your own prime time and down time. Examine the list with the activities you have to do and decide the time which is better for you to carry them out.

Prime Time	Down Time

Annex 4 (Notes Procrastination)

Design Your Own Anti-Procrastination Plan

Below are several lists of specific, concrete things you can do to confront and change your own tendencies to procrastinate. Choose several suggestions from among the four lists and put them into practice. If these activities work, keep on with them; if not, try different ones. Persist. Keep a record of your activities on the other side of this sheet.

First, schedule your tasks for your project.

-Write down a list of the tasks you must undertake to complete your project. Set priorities among these. Mark each one off as you complete it...and reward yourself.

-Start with the most unpleasant task—to get it over with—and work down until you get to the easier ones.

-Do something daily on your project, even if it is only for 5 minutes. Write down two or three things you can do toward your task which you can accomplish in 5 minutes and then do one of them...and reward yourself.

-Schedule work on one of your avoided tasks so that it is contingent upon something you already normally do and enjoy. For example, "I'll work on my term paper in the library half an hour before going to play racquetball."

Second, take action!

-When it comes time to do your task and you are tempted to procrastinate, make yourself sit down for 5 minutes and think about what you are about to do.

-Envision the emotional and physical consequences of procrastinating—and of following through on your plan to work. After you think this over, go ahead and do what you judge best...with no apologies or second thoughts!

-Imagine how you would behave in the next hour or day if you were NOT a procrastinator. Get a clear picture in your mind—and then act out that role, pretend, for the next hour or day, that you are not a procrastinator. When you are done, evaluate your "acting": did you do a good job? How did it feel?

-When you feel an impulse to work on your project, follow up on it: do it at the moment you think of it and keep at it until you don't feel like it anymore.

-Decide on a specific reward for success—and/or a punishment for failure—at working on your task. Make it realistic and follow through. For example, you might decide that you won't take a bath on a day when you don't work on your paper.

Third, use your friends!

-Make a contract with a friend or teacher to get a specific task done.

-Make an appointment with a teacher, tutor, or someone who can consult with you on your project. Ask for help and advice about proceeding.

-Make a lunch or dinner date with a friend. Tell your friend that you want his or her support, that you want to talk about your feelings about your project, that you want him or her to encourage you.

-If you have something frightening to do—talking to a professor, for example—ask a friend to listen to you rehearse what you have to say, so that you can face and live through and cope with your fear.

Fourth, keep a journal!

-Every day, write in your journal to give yourself credit for what you have accomplished, to genuinely forgive yourself for backsliding, and to plan your next anti-procrastination activity.

-In your journal, identify rationalizations, confront yourself, and redirect yourself to your task.

-Recognize negative attitudes and write out positive, encouraging attitudes.

-If you get mad, write out all your frustrations and anger in your journal.

-If you make a mistake, write out the interesting, beneficial things you learned from it.

I. Reasons why we procrastinate

A. Emotional difficulties that lead to/stem from procrastination:

1. **LOW SELF-ESTEEM.** Thinking of yourself as inadequate and unworthy leads you to procrastinate and thereby to lower your self-esteem.

a. **Perfectionism.** If you equate your self-worth with high performance, then procrastination protects you against the risk of failure.

b. **Need for love.** If you feel that people will accept you only if you perform well, then procrastination protects you from the risk of rejection.

c. **Anticipating the Worst.** If you can only imagine disaster as an outcome of your performance, then procrastination protects you from anxiety.

d. **Self-judgment.** If you judge yourself too harshly, then procrastination protects you from self-hating guilt and shame.

e. **Depression.** If you feel overwhelmed, immobilized and helpless to perform, then procrastination protects you from hopelessness.

f. **Ακαμνη ταυτότητα/ Rigid Identity.** If your image of yourself as a procrastinator is a self-fulfilling prophecy, then procrastination protects you from having to change.

2. **LOW FRUSTRATION TOLERANCE.** If you are unwilling to do hard tasks or to delay gratification, if you wait for internal motivators or inspiration, then procrastination is a means of avoiding hassle/ταλαιωπίες/καβγάδες.

Clearinghouse <http://www.utexas.edu/cmhc/clearinghouse> Workshop on Procrastination, p. 21 Leader's Key to structured lecture on procrastination (cont.)

3. **HOSTILITY.** If you are disappointed in your demands on life, if you feel spiteful toward teachers or parents or bosses and fail to meet their expectations, procrastination is a means of rebellion.

B. "Legitimate" reasons for procrastination: Excuses

1. **Naiveté or ignorance:** "I didn't know I could do it." "I didn't know I was supposed to do that."

2. **Fixed habits:** "But I've always done it this way! It's so hard to change!"

3. **Inertia:** "I just can't seem to get started." "It's so hard to drop one thing and pick up another."

4. **Frailty of memory:** "I just forgot!"

5. **Skill deficiencies:** "But I don't know how!"

6. **Physical problems:** "I couldn't do it: I was sick."

7. **Appropriate delays:** "I'm waiting for the best time to do it." "I really need some creative leisure."

II. Frequently used procrastination tactics: How to procrastinate.

- A. Put it off until later.
- B. Wait on something else. "I can't start my term paper until the professor explains the assignment better!"
- C. Choose the immediate pleasurable opportunity. Seize the day.
- D. Day-dream and fantasize about what you are going to do (but don't actually do it).
- E. Lose yourself in TV, movies, music, books, magazines, entertainment.
- F. Act impulsively without thinking about intentions or consequences.
- G. Drink alcohol; do drugs; seek oblivion.
- H. Read the classics, listen to classical music, do reputable cultural activities as a substitute for acting.
- I. Develop a compulsive addiction (over-eating, smoking, running) that consumes your time and attention.
- J. Be passive. Wait for fate or circumstance to rescue you from having to act.

III. Frequently heard rationalizations

- A. "I work better under pressure."
- B. "I don't know how to do this right. I can't do it."
- C. "I really don't want to do this."
- D. "It really won't make a difference if I put this off."
- E. "I need to be in the mood to do this."
- F. "I know I can pull this off at the last minute."
- G. "I'll save myself time and effort if I wait and do this all at once."
- H. "This moment, this opportunity, will never come again."
- I. "Forces beyond my control keep me from doing this."
- J. "I've worked so hard, I just don't have any energy left."
- K. "No one really cares whether I do this or not."

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